

Research

ROLE OF MICROFINANCE INSTITUTIONS IN POVERTY REDUCTION EMPLOYMENT CREATION AND INCOME GENERATING ACTIVITIES IN GHANA

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Abstract: *The poor been provided with financial services like credit, insurance, savings, and investment as employment creation and poverty reduction technique has earned much importance in the country for the past decade. This article examines microfinance institutions' role in poverty reduction, employment creation, and income-generating activities in Ghana. Again, it determines whether the institution has helped in the reduction of poverty, improving the standard and condition of living of its clients/customers. Primary and secondary data were used. A total of 90 respondents were interviewed made up of customers with questionnaires and was analyzed using SPSS. From the investigation, the article found out that microfinance institutions have highly impacted positively and significantly on customers in the form of income generation, employment creation, reducing poverty, increasing the standard of living and household's well-being of the customers. Also, the emanated results from the questionnaires administered reveal a favorable relationship between microfinance, poverty reduction and employment creation since most of the beneficiaries attested to a level of improvement in their businesses through the loans they receive and also improvement in their living standards and conditions since they became part of the microfinance program. Aside from the positive impacts, the institution is not without problems/issues affecting its operations and growth. These problems/issues include Risk problem, regulatory issues, capacity building problem, and problems of information gathering and dissemination which if stakeholders address properly, the microfinance institution will continue to contribute meaningfully towards employment creation, reducing poverty and increasing incomes across the world not only in Ghana.*

Keywords: *Poverty Reduction, Employment Creation, Income Generations, Microfinance, Ghana.*

1. Introduction

This article investigates microfinance role in poverty alleviating, to know how the microfinance subsector does create employment to the poor and how income levels of the poor

change from low income to high income and low standard of living to a high standard. Microfinance proved to be a great instrument to fight poverty, create jobs, empower women, and empower low-income individuals and households, groups and community members in the country. It is also a great instrument in economic development through helping low-income people, groups, a community in society to be part of the financial and social intermediation. The microfinance scheme also provides active poor people with financial opportunities to better their lives and to enhance their living standards and wellbeing. The subsector is a key strategy that leads to the revitalization of the Ghanaian economy through employment generation, poverty alleviating, women empowerment and the enhancement of the standards of the living of the poor.

The microfinance institutions in Ghana's has lots of significant. Because it played an important role in the country's process of financial intermediation process and to the lives of poor & low-income individuals. Rutherford, (1999) said, microfinance is showed that, is a great instrument for human development and poverty relief. Microfinance can also not be denied by the saying that it alleviates poverty. The stakeholders thus Governments, donors' agencies, financial regulators, policymakers, managers, and customers all agreed to the fact that microfinance contributes to poverty reduction, but as to how the poverty will be reduced by the institution is still a matter of concern hence the need for this article to investigate or find out how poverty is reduced through the institution. In Ghanaian situation, most microfinance institutions are established with the aims and objectives of targeting the productive poor through socio-economic empowerment, creation of employment, creating of awareness, income-generating activities, self-employment generating, and the rural poor targeting.

The objectives of the article include: expatiating how the microfinance institution has contributed towards reducing poverty, to discuss microfinance institutions role in Employment creation in Ghana, and evaluate the microfinance schemes impact on the poor in terms of income generation and to examine poor people's level of participation and outreach in the microfinance program. The below questions were answered in the article: Does microfinance institutions contribute to poverty reduction in Ghana? What roles do microfinance institutions play in employment creation in Ghana? Do microfinance schemes have impacts on the poor in terms of income generation? What is the poor people's level of participation and outreach in the microfinance program?

For unemployment to be reduced, the active poor needs a productive job which will lead to high incomes. Three major things through employment to alleviate poverty must be undertaken: That is, generating employment, increase employability and labor market must be made efficient. Morduch (1999) concluded that there is hope when providing low-income people with financial services because their level of poverty reduction while economic & social amenities will all be improved and transformed fundamentally. Concerning credit and poverty alleviation, Dr. Mohammed Yunus (1999) argues that microfinance cannot eliminate poverty at once because it is not a miracle cure but poverty can end for many and also help reduce the severity of it on other individuals. He established the Grameen Bank of Bangladesh which serves as a reference point in the microfinance industry.

1.2 Microfinance and Poverty Reduction

The microfinance industry is viewed as a key development tool not only in reducing poverty but also for financial inclusion in most parts of the world. Though the microfinance sub-sector started in Ghana in the 1950s, as a form of Susu in northern Ghana through the activities of the Canadian missionaries, in the 1970s, Mohammed Yunus formally founded the Grameen Bank which formally, is the first microfinance bank to be established. In the 1990s microfinance

popularly gain global attention which led to the organization of a summit in 1997 with thousands of delegates and hundreds of countries attended the summit. Quaraishi, (2007) at the summit said: Hundred million of the poorest people will be reached with financial services that they lack such as credit, insurance, savings, and investment, and other services were agreed by delegates by 2005. At UN General Assembly in December 2003, they announced the international microcredit year as the year 2005. Microfinance institutions in Ghana offer credit to these low-income individuals who are their customers and they work to reduce their poverty.

2. Related Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Review of Literature

Micro-credit is a small amount of loan/credit issued to the poor, low-income individuals who are unemployed without collateral for them to start a business with and have better living standards. The type of credit given to them is a short term loan and the amount is also small. This is mostly from 6- 12 months with weekly or monthly installments. The interest rates on the credit are given seems much higher as compared to the traditional banks charged rate. This is because the earning on the interest should cover at least the probability of default rate, administrative cost, and inflation. Microfinance is a financial institution that offers services that are small-scale like loans, savings, investment, insurance which are offered to individuals who do small businesses, farming, etc. and the goods and services produced are recycled, sold repaired, working for wage rate, earned profit from the small businesses, renting outlands, vehicles, machinery, tools and animal draft, and to the people and group of people in developing countries, urban and rural areas. (Robinson, 2001). In a broader definition, microfinance goes beyond microcredits, rather includes other services, offered to low-income & poor people. Other services that improve the lives and living standards of the poor is linked up with lending and not just small credits (Bauer, Chytilova, Morduch, 2008). Infrastructure and health care system improvement is also part of micro-financing. Most programs of microfinance institutions are connected with business training, technical training, educational, retaining and or savings programs.

Measuring Outreach

The Microfinance sector capacity & ability to provide a financial services that are of high quality to a large number of clients, female participation high percentage, the number of the institutions branches, institution's size, the institution's total asset & value, total value of outstanding loans, average deposit size and credit, amount of savings/deposit are considered as the indicators in measuring outreach of an institution (Gumel, 2011). While Schreiner (2002) illustrates six (6) different frameworks in the measuring of the outreach of microfinance institutions to include: the depth, breadth, scope, length, the cost to the users and the worth of users. Similarly, SEEP, (2005) indicated that the microfinance outreach is measured by so many factors and to mention a few of them are: number of active clients, the portfolio of gross loan, the number of customers & active borrowers in the institution.

Employment Meaning

Employment simply means the state or act of having a paid job whether fully employed or partly employed. Thus, utilizing something or one's time. Full employment is an economic term whereby all the labor resources available are effectively and efficiently used. Employment is a relationship that exists between two parties, based on an agreed contract where the work is done is paid for, and where one of the parties is an employee and the other employer which may be a company, profit organization, non-profit organization, co-operatives entity where the employee works to earn payment or in a return for payment. There are five main types of employment in

economics: permanent jobs or fixed-term employment, casual employment/employees, Apprentices or trainees/employees, the employment agency staff who are also called labor hire and the contract and subcontract staff/the hired staff. Also, there are three main types of employment status which are, employees, workers or employers self-employed persons. Employment creation as to do with the number of jobs created in a country for citizen engagement and recruitment. Unemployment is when a person or an individual is searching for a job actively and not able to find a job/work. The unemployment rate is used to measure unemployment and is the number of individuals who are unemployed by the number of individuals who are employed. Unemployment is of different types: seasonal, frictional, structural, cyclical, technological.

Income Generation

Income generation is an intervention or activity that impacts vocational skills or commodities or capital provision which enhances the individual capacity or groups to generate income. Some potential income-generating activities are Agricultural production, livestock establishment, shop-keeping activities, traders, food sellers, handicrafts, food drying.

Meaning of Poverty

The International Labour Organization (ILO) conceptualizes poverty as people who live below \$2 per day. At the International Labour Conference in Geneva in 2003, the ILO provides policies and advises on how poverty can be reduced in the World (ILO, 2003). "Poor individuals can also save and they want to save, when the people have not saved, then is due to not having the opportunity but not lack of ability or capacity". (Rutherford, 1999). In Ghana, Poverty is defined as many dimensions which are consisted of illiteracy/no education, lower-income/lacks income, malnutrition/lack of well-balanced diet, ill-health, and insecurity. Sense of powerlessness and exclusion (GSS, 2007). Obadan (1996) classified poor people as those who think the amount of money they spend per day is below the United Nations' \$1.25 purchasing power parity (PPP).

2.2 Empirical Review

Adjei et al. (2009) used the Snapi Aba Trust of Ghana as a case to examine the microfinance institution's role in asset building & reducing poverty. They established that beneficiaries could purchase durables, provide better education to their children and to cater for their health care expenses of their households. They also concluded that customers' participation in the microfinance program own personal savings deposits and become members of welfare schemes that provided insurance pay debts off due to illness or death. Similarly, Coleman (1999) argued that there is an insignificant impact regarding micro-credit accessibility in household wealth improvement in the north-eastern part of Thailand from a conducted survey of sample households. However, a similar study by Coleman (2006) also in north-eastern Thailand found a positive effect on household welfare among committee members who were granted access to financing when the sample was categorized into general beneficiaries and committee members. It was observed that the insignificant impact was limited to the general beneficiaries. Again, a study by Bebczuk and Haimovich (2007) in some Latin American countries examined the impact of credit on beneficiaries with a household survey. Findings from the study showed an increase in household income and education.

3 Methodology

The methodology of this article is a descriptive and analytical research design. The selected method is mainly quantitative. The primary source of data for this article was by conducting a field survey, interviews with the support of a questionnaire. Secondary data was also used as a source of information and were gathered from microfinance books, journals, dissertations/thesis

published, and the internet. There were over five hundred microfinance institutions in Ghana as at the start of data collection (September 2018) in the various regions of the country. Thus, registered microfinance institutions. Out of the total population of microfinance institutions, 90 individuals/respondents were purposively and conveniently selected as the sample size from some selected microfinance institutions for this article. Quantitative analysis tools were used in assessing the microfinance institutions role in poverty reduction and the creation of employment in Ghana. Also, other indicators used in assessing the income generation of the active rural poor through the microfinance sub-sector. The Ninety (90) respondents interviewed were due to their time and conveniences to be interview using questionnaires for the customers. Few employees and managers who could not have time for face to face interviews with the interview guides were also interviewed using the questionnaire. The results from the field data collection were analyzed quantitatively using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) and with the support of statistical and frequency distribution tools like, numbers, tables, frequencies, percentages, pie chart, bar chart, and histograms.

4. Findings

Table 1: Gender of Respondents

Considering the gender issues is very important in any research of this kind. The researcher takes note of the sex of the respondents both the employers, employees and the customers. The below table shows the statistics of the respondents.

Respondents Gender	Frequencies	Percentages
Male	62	69
Female	28	31
Total	90	100

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

From the field responses, out of the total sample size of 90 respondents', the frequency of the male respondent is 62 which constitutes 69 percent while the female respondents' frequency is 28 representing 31 percent of the total interview. The meaning here is that the number of male workers in the microfinance institutions far exceeds that of female workers. It was observed that microfinance in Ghana was constituted and managed by the majority of men. This is due to the technical and operational involvement of the institution's operations. Also, more women are involved in petty trading and other business than in banking industries because most of them lack education and experience in the country.

Table 2: The Respondents Age

Ages of the participants were grouped according to 4 groups. From the findings, the respondents were made up of more youth than the aged. More of them were under age forty. This means that the working population and the customers of the institutions are both young and energetic. The following table explains further the age categories of the respondents.

Class	Frequency	Percentage
15-25	23	26
25-35	34	38
35-45	29	32
45-Above	4	4
Total	90	100

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

According to the responses from the field, the age range 25 - 35 represents the highest frequency of 34. That is out of the total population interviewed, constituting 38 percent. The interviewees in this class are those actively involved in the running of the MFI in the country. The next actively involved are the age group 35-45 with a frequency of 29 representing 33 percent of the interviewed people. With age group 15 - 25 years having a frequency of 23 and 26 percent of the population, most of them are part-time workers and are school going students who help the institution on weekend collections or work during free times. Some of these workers are those who most of the times lead the institution to bankruptcy and collapse. The remaining respondents are the age group 45 and above with only 4 percent out of the sample size interviewed. We observe that the ages 15 to 25 are less involved in the operations of the institution likewise the aged age 45 and above. The actively involved are the youth who are under 40 years and who fall between 25 to 40 years having greater than 50 percent of the total interviewed population.

Table 3: Educational level

The level of education/educational background of participants was asked to know their literacy level. It also helps know the skills level of the participants. It is believed generally that, the higher/ more the level of education of the participants, the higher their knowledge and understanding of the concepts of microfinance and hence better result and the lower the level of education, the lower the understanding and knowledge. All things being equal. The table below indicated the educational qualification of the respondents from the data collected.

Level of Education	Frequency	Percentage
Secondary School	5	5
Diploma / HND	43	48
Bachelor	34	38
Masters	8	9

PhD	0	0
Total	90	100

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

The academic qualification of the respondents from the researcher's field data collection which comprises owners/managers, staff/employees, and the customers/beneficiaries of the microfinance institution was shown in the above table. The distribution of the population points out that 48 percent of the respondents representing 43 of the population have completed a Higher National Diploma (HND) followed by 38 percent representing 34 frequency of the people interviewed who have also graduated from the university with degree qualifications. Again, 9 percent of the respondents representing 8 of the total interviewed graduated with a Master's degree while 5 percent of the respondents are Secondary School graduates. The researcher observed during the study that, upon the academic qualification of the respondents, most of them still lack knowledge and understanding of the concepts of microfinance. This makes the operations very difficult and making some of the institutions unsustainable. They operate based on experience and support from other staff of different banks.

Table 4: Marriage Status

Marriage Status	Frequencies	Percentages
Married	48	53
Singled	26	29
Separated	7	8
Living Together	6	7
Divorced	3	3
Total	90	100

Source: Primary Data 2018.

Of the responses, 53 percent of the interviewees are married while 29 percent of the population interviewed are singled. 8 percent got separated while 7 percent are living together with partners but are not formally married. Only 3 percent of the respondent said they have divorced. We observed that married couples are more with the highest percentage of 53 percent.

Table 5: Workers Experience

The table below indicates the experience of staff and customers based on the years the respondents have been working or been with the microfinance institutions as customers or staff. It is believed that the more years one has with an institution, the more the experience acquired and the less the years of work, the lower the experience all things being equal.

Number of Years	Frequency	Percentage
One (1) Year	13	15
Two (2) Years	31	34
Three (3) Years	26	29
Four (4) Years	11	12
Five (5) Years And More	9	10
Total	90	100

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

From the findings, 15 percent of respondents have one year of working experience and 34 percent interviewees with two years' experience. While 29 percent have three years of working experience, 12 percent have Four years' experience of work and finally 10 percent with five years and more working experiences.

Table 6: Regional Location of Microfinance Institution

Since the study is in the entire regions of Ghana, there is a need to know the number of interviews in each of the Regions. The researcher tries to explore the locations of the microfinance institution so questions about the region of the location were ask to the respondents. All the ten (10) regions were taking into consideration and the below table indicates the classifications and responses from the Regional findings.

Number	Location / Region	Frequency	Percentage	Total
1	Greater Accra	35	39	39
2	Central	5	6	45
3	Western,	4	4	49
4	Ashanti	8	9	58
5	Eastern	5	6	64
6	Volta	2	2	66
7	Brong Ahafo	10	11	77
8	Northern	15	17	94
9	Upper East	4	4	98
10	Upper West	2	2	100

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

From the table above, it can be seen that Accra has the highest number of MFIs been interviewed followed by the Northern region with 39 percent and 17 percent respectively. The next highest was the Brong Ahafo region with 11 percent of the total interviewed then followed by the Ashanti region with 9 percent. The above regions were having the majority of interviews due to the availability and willingness of the institution's management and customers to be interviewed. Eastern region has 6 percent interviews, Western and Upper East regions have 4 percent each while Volta and Upper West regions have 2 percent each. We ascertained that, from a total number of a microfinance institution in Ghana, Greater Accra alone is having over 60 percent and the rest is in the other 9 Regions hence the reason why more interviews in that Region. These are the number of respondents interviewed in each region not the number of microfinance institutions.

6.1 Products/Service provided by Microfinance in Ghana

Different products/services have been provided to customers. Both the service providers and the beneficiaries mentioned some of the products and services rendered and received to include: Loans/credit, Savings/deposits, Current accounts, fixed deposits, micro insurances, mobile money transfers, remittances.

Table 7: Loans Received from Microfinance Institutions

Table 7 below illustrates the number of customers who benefited from the loans offered by the microfinance institution in Ghana. Out of 90 respondents, 54 said they are beneficiaries from the loans while the remaining 36 said they are not beneficiaries. Different customers use these loans for different purposes and the income generated from it too was used for a variety of purposes. Some were able to pay back the loans and others defaulted from the findings of the study.

Loan received	Frequency	Percentage
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Yes	54	60
No	36	40
Total	90	100

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

From the findings, 60 percent of the respondents said they are loan beneficiaries from the microfinance institution while 40 percent mentioned that, they did not go for a loan from the institution.

Table 8: Loan repayment to Microfinance Institutions

This table below gives statistics of loan beneficiaries of microfinance institutions. Out of the total number of those who went for the loans, the number of those who returned and those who refuse to repay. Below is the breakdown:

Loan returned / repaid	Frequencies	Percentages
Yes	42	78
No	12	22
Total	54	100

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

From the findings, 78 percent of the respondents repaid the loans given to them by the microfinance institution while 22 percent refused to pay back the loans. We realized that the majority of the loan beneficiaries repay their loans and minority refuse too.

Table 9: Uses of Loans from Microfinance Institutions

The below table indicates the uses of the credit/loans that the beneficiaries or customers received from the microfinance institutions. It was used for different purposes.

Uses of Credit from MFI	Frequencies	Percentages
Starting new businesses	36	40
Expansion of existing businesses	18	20
Increase number of products	24	27
Hire more employees	12	13
Total	90	100

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

The loans that were received from the microfinance by the respondents were used appropriately by the majority of the respondents. From the interviewed, some of the customers attested to the fact that they use the loans to start a new business altogether. They said without the loans from the microfinance program they cannot start anything new on their own. According to them, microfinance helps them to establish a business and also employ a few workers to help in the running of the businesses. Aside from the starting of new business by some of the clients, other beneficiaries also use the loans to expand their business. Other branches were opened and some increase the number of their products and services. They said this increases their profit level and their living standards.

Uses of Loans from Microfinance Institutions

- Start new business
- Expand existing business
- Increase number of products
- Hire more employees

40 percent used the loans to start a new business as can be seen from the above pie chart and 20 percent expand existing business with it. 27 percent mentioned that, they use the credit received from the microfinance institution to increase the number of products in their businesses and only 13 percent said, they hire new staff to help in the running of the business.

Table 9.1 the Use of Income from Loans by Beneficiaries

Table 8 below indicates how the beneficiaries of the loans from the microfinance program utilize the income they get after using the credit. While others use them to expand their businesses, some use it for their daily expenses. From the three Northern Regions of Ghana, most of the beneficiaries said they use their income for agricultural purposes to buy fertilizer and other farm inputs which help them to get a good harvest. While the beneficiaries from the southern part of Ghana attested that they used the income for savings, investment and other purposes.

No	Uses of the Income from loans	Frequency	Percentage
1	To start a new business	16	18
2	For business expansion	11	12
3	For savings	10	11
4	For investment	9	10
5	Payment of children's school fees	5	6
6	Investment in Agricultural	8	9
7	Hiring of new staffs	2	2
8	Building of a house	1	1
9	Household consumption	7	8
10	Medicals	3	3
11	To pay other loans	5	6
12	To marry	2	2
13	To build new skills / upgrade knowledge	3	3
14	For growth and family up keeping	6	7
15	For house rent payment	2	2

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

The table above indicates various usages of the income generated from the credit used by the customers from the microfinance institution. The majority of the beneficiaries concluded that

the credit has been very beneficiary to them because they can start some businesses by themselves now and others said they use it for payment of their children's school fees. From the responses of the beneficiaries, a greater percentage of the respondents use the income to start a new business (18 percent) and 12 percent use the income to expand their business while 10 percent and 9 percent use the income for savings and investment respectively. The farmers also use the income to buy their farming products and this is represented by 8 percent out of the total. Again, for household consumption, growth and family up keeping is 7 percent and 6 percent while 5 percent of the beneficiaries each said they use it to pay children school fees and payment of other loans from a different institution. We realized from the findings that, most of the respondents utilize the loans and are making good investments and paying back while some of the beneficiaries refuse to pay the Bank but rather repay other loans from different Banks.

Table 10 Role of Microfinance Institution in Ghana

Microfinance institution in Ghana plays a great role in the country's economic development since its inception. Some of the roles are: Microfinance Institutions helps to reduce poverty, microfinance create employments and helps both men and women by providing them with loans, support small and medium enterprises with credit, microfinance provide the poor with banking products/services and support by providing low income & active poor people with credit/loans.

No	Role of Microfinance Institutions	Frequency	Percentage
1	Microfinance Institutions helps to reduce poverty	16	18
2	Microfinance create employments	14	16
3	Help both men and women by providing them with Loans	9	10

4	Helps SMEs with credit	5	6
5	Microfinance provide the poor with banking products and services	7	8
6	Provide the poor with credit / Loans	4	4
7	Help the poor to come up with new businesses	2	2
8	Microfinance helps in business expansion	3	3
9	Provide the active poor with startup capital	2	2
10	Microfinance helps in Economic development	6	7
11	Microfinance increase the living standards of the poor.	5	6
12	The banking population in Ghana is increased through Microfinance	2	2
13	Microfinance institutions help to empower the women	8	9
14	Developing and improvement of SMEs	3	3
15	Provision of services and advises (such as financial advisory services, financial training, money transfer and micro insurances services)	4	4

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

From both the table and the diagram, it was indicated that MFIs play a key role in the Ghanaian economy. Statistics of roles played based on the respondents responses during the interviews are: Microfinance institutions helps to reduce poverty (18 percent), Microfinance create employments (16 percent), Help both men and women by providing them with Loans (10), Helps SMEs with credit (6 percent), Microfinance provide the poor with banking products and services (8 percent), Provide the poor with credit / Loans (4 percent), Help the poor to come up with new businesses (2 percent), Microfinance helps in business expansion (3 percent), Provide the active poor with startup capital (2 percent), Microfinance helps in Economic development (7 percent), Microfinance increase the living standards of the poor (6 percent), the banking population in Ghana

is increased through microfinance (2 percent), Microfinance institutions help to empower the women (9 percent), Developing & improvement of SMEs (3 percent), Provision of services and advises (4 percent) these include (financial advisory services, financial training, money transfer, and micro insurances services).

Table 11: Issues and Problems Microfinance Institutions Faced

Though microfinance institutions play a wonderful role in the country's economic development, the institutions still have some problems facing it. From the researchers' findings, the respondents mentioned problems or issues such as regulations and supervision from regulators, credit defaults from customers, lack of support from the Government, high-interest rates, and Ghana cedi depreciation as the main problems they faced. The below table indicates the remaining problems according to the findings from the respondents.

No	Issues and Problems Microfinance Institutions faced	Frequency	Percentage
1	Risk problem (credit risk, financial and systematic risk)	11	12
2	Regulatory issues (National, formal, semi-formal and informal institutions)	13	14
3	Capacity building problem (human, infrastructure, and funding)	5	5
4	The marginalized and vulnerable targeting issues (the people with disability, the women and the youth)	6	7
5	Mechanisms for loan delivering problems	5	5
6	Problem of clients and their savings protection	7	8
7	Lack/low understanding of definitions & concepts of MFIs	6	7
8	Issues of microfinance institutions categorization	4	4
9	Problems of gathering and dissemination information	7	8
10	Issues in MFIs collaboration and coordination	6	7
11	MFIs target group classification problem	2	2
12	Problem of researching, monitoring and evaluation by the institutions	6	7
13	Government inadequate support for microfinance institutions.	3	3
14	Problem of panic withdrawals due to collapse of other MFIs	6	7
15	Problem of the Ghana currency depreciation.	3	3

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

From the findings, management, employees, and customers stated the above as the problems/issues that the microfinance institutions faced in Ghana which in one way or the other hinders the operations of the institutions. Problems with regulation and supervision are seen as the greatest issue with the highest percentage of 12 followed by the credit defaults and collapse of other microfinance institutions which leads to panic withdrawal from customers of 11 percent each as seen in the above table. Lack of support from the government of Ghana is also an issue facing the institution and inadequate understanding of the definitions and concepts of microfinance by some employees and customers constituting 7 percent each.

Table 12: Key Poverty Reduction and Employment Strategies in Ghana

In Ghana, according to the respondents, there are a lot of poverty reduction strategies taking place in the country and employment strategies all targeting poverty reduction and employment creation aside from the microfinance institutions. That, these strategies were carried out by the past and current governments, the ministries, departments, and agencies. The strategies from the findings include: 1. National youth employment program 2. Youth employment authorities 3. Poverty reduction strategies (GPRS 1 & GPRS 11) 4. Agricultural development banks 5. Poverty alleviation program 6. Ghana national poverty eradication program 7. Women empowerment, 8. Universal basic education 9. Free senior high schools, 10. Microfinance banking schemes and 11. Rural and community banks. All the above strategies and programs are targeted towards empowerment, employment creation and poverty reduction in the country.

No	Poverty Reduction and Employment Creation Strategies	Frequency	Percentage
1	National Youth Employment Program (NYEP)	12	13
2	Youth Employment Authorities (YEA)	5	6
3	Ghana Poverty Reduction Strategy (GPRS I)	7	8
4	Agricultural Development Banks (ADB)	3	3

5	Poverty Alleviation Program (PAP)	5	6
6	Ghana National Poverty Eradication Program (GNPEP)	5	6
7	Women Empowerment Programs	6	7
8	Free Compulsory Universal Basic Education (FCUBE)	3	3
9	Ghana Poverty Reduction Strategy (GPRSII)	7	8
10	Rural and Community Banks (RCBs)	4	4
11	Microfinance Banking Schemes (MFS)	9	10
12	Free Senior High School (FSHS)	6	7
13	Voluntary National Service (VNS)	4	4
14	National Service Scheme (NSS)	4	4
15	Nation Builders Cooperation (NABCO)	10	11

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

According to the interviewees' responses on the poverty reduction and employment creation strategies in Ghana, the below are the factors and the number of individuals who indicated that: National Youth Employment Program 12 respondent mentioned that which is 13 percent of the total population interviewed. 5 people said youth employment authorities which are 6 percent of the population and 7 respondents made mentioned Ghana poverty reduction strategy I that is 8 percent of the population. Agricultural development banks were also mentioned by 3 people indicating 3 percent while Women Empowerment Programs 6 interviewees and 7 percent. Poverty alleviation program and Ghana national poverty eradication program 5 people and that is 6 percent of the entire interviewed population each. Free Compulsory Universal Basic Education 3 individuals constituting 3 percent of the population and Ghana poverty reduction strategy II 7 people respondent and that is 8 percent. Rural and community banks and Voluntary National Service 4 respondents and 4 percent each while Microfinance Banking Schemes 9 people indicating 10 percent. Free Senior High School is 7 percent and 6 respondents and National service Scheme also 4 individuals with 4 percent. Finally, 10 respondents constituting 11 percent made mentioned of Nation Builders Cooperation.

Table 13: Ways to Reduce Poverty in Ghana

According to the respondents, there are so many ways to reduce poverty in Ghana which is referred to as the solutions to Ghana poverty according to some respondents. Some of the solutions the respondents mentioned include: Jobs / Employment creation, Women empowerment and the Girl child education, the minimum wages, and salaries should be increased, reduction in minimum capital requirement by regulators from BoG, encouraging establishment of more MFIs into the system, tax exemption from some of the institution, providing very good health care facilities especially delivering services, making the spending's of government transparent, there should be good sanitation portable and clean drinking water in all communities in Ghana, a nutritious and well-balanced diet for children especially the infants in homes and schools, Gender equality making and unmaking inequalities and finally managing Sovereign Debt.

No	Ways to Reduce Poverty in Ghana	Frequency	Percentage
1	More Jobs / Employment Creation	12	14
2	Women Empowerment	4	4
3	Encouraging girl child education	3	3
4	Accessible good roads	7	8
5	Encouraging the establishment of more microfinance institutions in the system,	14	16
6	Managing Sovereign Debt	1	1
7	Implementing Gender equality and discouraging inequalities	2	2
8	A well-balanced diet and very nutritious diet for children and infants both in homes and at schools,	4	4
9	Providing good sanitation, portable and clean drinking water in all communities of Ghana,	5	6
10	Reduction in minimum capital, reserve, and liquidity requirement by regulators	11	12
11	Tax exemption for some of the institutions	2	2
12	providing very good health care facilities by Government	5	6
13	Minimum wages and salaries should be increased,	9	10
14	Delivering services and government spending should be transparent,	3	3
15	Effective and markets accessibility in all communities	8	9

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

Table 14: Types of Businesses in Ghana Microfinance Institutions

The interviewees mentioned several types of business in Ghana that are engaged in the microfinance program. These businesses according to the customers of the institutions get credit from the microfinance program which helps them build their businesses and put it into good standing. Some of the businesses mentioned include Dressmaking, barbering, petty trading, Food selling, metal works, bread baking, books and stationery, farming, leather works, transport owners and other small and medium enterprises. We ascertained that the credit collected are put into different uses by different clients.

No	Types of Businesses in Ghana MFIs	Frequency	Percentage
1	Dressmaking	14	16
2	Barbering,	9	10
3	Petty trading	7	8
4	Food selling,	5	5
5	Metal works,	4	4
6	Bread baking,	8	9
7	Farming,	13	14
8	Leather works	2	2
9	Transportation Businesses	5	5
10	Books and stationary	6	7
11	Small and medium enterprises	11	12
12	Retail businesses	7	8

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

According to the findings, Dressmaking is (16 percent), Barbering is (10 percent), Petty trading is (8 percent), Food selling is (5 percent), Metalwork (4 percent), Bread baking (9 percent), Farming (14 percent), and Leatherworks (2 percent). Transportation Businesses (5 percent), Books and stationary (7 percent), Small and medium enterprises (12 percent), Retail businesses (8 percent).

Table 15: The Role of Ghana Government in Microfinance Institutions

The government of Ghana has a key role to play in the operations & survival of the institutions in the country. The Government has to ensure that favorable policies are formulated, a good regulatory framework and best monitoring and supervision style is adopted to help sustain the microfinance institutions within the country. Rhyne and Otero (2006:19) indicated that most microfinance institutions have flourished and sustained where the government keeps itself separate from policies, allow the market to determine interest rates, independent allocation of credit from other issues and lending also independent from the Government. Through the Ghana poverty reduction Strategies 1 and 11 implemented by the Government in the country (GPRS I and GPRS II), it is obvious that Microfinance in the Country is considered by the government to reduce and fight poverty in Ghana and to help create employment for the poor. The government should, therefore, review its laws, rules, and regulations towards the microfinance sector to implement favorable policies to motivate and encourage MFIs in Ghana so that more customers and the public will have lots of confidence with the microfinance sub-sector.

No	The Role of Ghana Government in MFIs	Frequency	Percentage
1	Favorable Government Policies formulated	16	18
2	Good regulatory framework	14	16
3	Best monitoring and supervision style adopted	9	10
4	Effective regulatory guidelines and principles implemented	7	8
5	Interest rates determined by the market	8	9
6	Credit allocation independent from Government	4	4
7	Lending independent from the Government.	2	2

8	Effective implementation of GPRS 1 and 11	7	8
9	Laws, rules and regulations of microfinance sub-sector should be reviewed	5	5
10	Creation of more job opportunities / MFIs	6	7
11	Government supporting microfinance institutions	9	10
12	Other roles	3	3

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

The respondents' responses from the findings indicated that, Favorable Government Policies formulated 18 percent, Good regulatory framework 16 percent, Best monitoring and supervision style adopted 10 percent, Effective regulatory guidelines, and principles implemented 8 percent, Interest rates determined by the market 9 percent, Credit allocation independent from Government 4 percent, Lending independent from the Government 2 percent, Effective implementation of GPRS 2 percent, Laws, rules and regulations of microfinance sub-sector should be reviewed 5 percent, Creation of more job opportunities / MFIs 7 percent, Government supporting microfinance institutions 10 percent, 3 percent.

Table 16: Development Agendas and Microfinance Institutions

Aside from the government of Ghana, other development partners also endorsed microfinance institutions in the reduction of poverty and helping the poor through several ways as mentioned by some of the respondents during the interviewed. Those development agendas worldwide that endorse microfinance in the alleviation of poverty are The Declarations of 2005 & 2004 by G8, United Nations World Summit of 2005, and Commission on Private Sector Development, the Brussels Program of Action, Commission of Africa and many other more. The table gives the number of responses by each of the respondents.

No	Development Agendas and MFIs	Frequency	Percentage
1	The Declarations of 2005 & 2004 by G8	18	20
2	United Nations World Summit of 2005	22	24
3	Private Sector Development Commission	9	10
4	Brussels Program of Action	5	6
5	African Commission.	7	8
6	The G20 financial inclusion expert Group (FIEG)	14	15
7	Other (The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision)	15	17

Source: Primary Data, 2018.

The table above concluded that many development Agendas endorsed microfinance institutions as a key poverty reduction strategies. According to the respondents, 18 (20 percent) respondents mentioned G8 Declarations of 2005 and 2004 and 22 (24 percent) said the United Nations World Summit of 2005. The Private Sector Development commission and Brussels Program of Action said 9 (10 percent) and 5 (6 percent) respectively. 7 and 15 respondents again made mention of (8 percent) and 17 (percent) as the African Commission and the G20 financial inclusion expert Group (FIEG). The remaining interviewees said other development partners and agendas like (The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision and others) to be 15 (17 percent).

5. Discussions

It shows from the foregoing that: microfinance institution plays an instrumental role in Ghana's economic development though some problems and issues are facing the sub-sector. Some of these problems and issues among others are credit default from customers, improper regulations and supervision, high-interest rate, high minimum capital requirement, lack of government and donor support, inappropriate reporting standards, and panic withdrawal due to the collapse of other microfinance institution.

- The loan beneficiaries who are engaged in the microfinance program have different years of participation. It is observed that more than 80 percent of beneficiaries of microfinance schemes have come from cities and not rural areas.
- More so, the interest rate charged on microfinance loans is much higher than the interest rate charged in traditional or conventional banks. It is found out that, about 80 percent of the loan beneficiaries utilized their credit for productive purposes.
- Furthermore, the types of income-generating activities the clients carried out include farming (animal husbandry, poultry farming, dairy farming, fish farming, crops, and cereals), manufacturing and so on.
- Again, the study found out that, microfinance program in Ghana help to create employment by issuing loans to the befitting customers. The beneficiaries of these credits attested to the fact that the credit given to them through the microfinance program was utilized by them because they used it to established businesses of different types and get income out of it.
- Some of the loan beneficiaries said they ploughed back the profit and others conclude that they use it for savings, investment, farming, household consumption, and other purposes.
- The results of the study also reveal that microfinance institutions offered credits to their customers to do businesses, get profit from the businesses, and use the income to expand the businesses, save and be able to repay the loans.
- Additionally, the study observed that, the income that the clients of the microfinance program gained help the poor to increase their living standards and condition. This in a way help reduce their poverty levels. The youth in Ghana continuously complained about unemployment in the country increasing and the poor people becoming poorer. Through microfinance and their programs, some of the poor people gain employment and are now working as self-employed and making ends meet.
- In furtherance of the above, the paper suggests a possible way to help reduce poverty, reduce the problems and issues to create more employments for the poor.

Some of the ways to reduce poverty in Ghana include women empowerment and girl child educational encouragement, providing very good health care and delivery facilities, there should be good and proper sanitation, portable and very clean drinking water in all communities in the country.

- Despite the above, to reduce the challenges of the institutions, the government and donors should support the microfinance program with funds, there should be currency appreciation, proper monitoring, and supervision from Bank of Ghana, capacity building of the employers and employees by ministry of finance of the country (policy-making body), and there should be proper training on good reporting standards by the regulators (bank of Ghana).
- In spite of the above mentioned, for more employment to be created, there should be a reduction in minimum capital requirement by bank of Ghana financial regulators so that more microfinance institutions can be established in order to increase jobs, there should be tax exemption for some of the institutions, customers should pay the loans given to them so that other clients can also benefit from the program.
- Finally, if the government, policymakers, donors, management and all other stakeholders of the microfinance sub-sector would support the institution, the mission and vision of the institutions will be achieved in the country thereby sustaining the microfinance sub-sector.

6. Summary

Microfinance roles in Employment creation and Poverty reduction cannot all be stated and the institutions are overwhelming amazing with proper regulation, effective policies, and a conducive environment in place in a country. The institution encourages self-independent, creates employment for the poor through the credit given which intends to reduce the poverty level of the clients.

Besides, the small and medium enterprises who are beneficiaries of microfinance institutions, to some extent export their goods, effectively and efficiently utilize local raw materials in the country and this has impacted positively and significantly to the economic development of Ghana. For the great potentials of microfinance to effectively continue, it is important that the government encourages more microfinance institutions into areas where it is lacking, support them with funds, encourage more entrepreneurs by creating social amenities such as water, good roads and encourage technical education.

Furthermore, policies should be reviewed on business ventures like excessive payment of tax which have effects on the income levels because that discourages entrepreneurs & potential entrepreneurs.

More so, we realized that microfinance in Ghana does not get all the necessary support needed from most of the stakeholders like the Ministries Departments & Agencies, and from other banks and institutions. The above was from the respondents' responses to some of the problems they are facing in Ghana as microfinance institution's operators.

7. Conclusion

Following the discussed point above, it clear and obvious that, the institution plays a key role in uplifting poor people, and also helps in increasing their income levels, their standard of living, poverty reduction through the credit provided and employment created. With the support of the above points, it can be concluded in the study that:

There exists no doubt in saying that, "microfinance has a positive impact on alleviating poverty in Ghana". The subsector supports poor people by increasing their living standards and their households in the study area. The microcredit provided by the institutions helps in reducing poverty and dependency as well as the upliftment of the poor people's socio-economic status.

In Ghana, the microfinance scheme is a Strategy for economic development, women empowerment, job creation, and empowerment of low-income households. Microfinance institution plays a positive role in employment provision to low-income households in the country.

Again, from the findings stated above, the researcher can conclude that the importance of microfinance institutions role in economic development, increasing the standard of living through employment creation and credit issued to customers in the country cannot be overemphasized.

Also, from the discussion, it shows that microfinance is an important and useful tool for reducing the problem of poverty, unemployment reduction, and small & medium business stimulation in the country. The dynamic nature of the institutions as made it very clear that the products and services offered to poor people have no best way.

It was also indicated that the customers received, not only deposit-taking, and microcredit but also remittances, and micro-insurance services. Some of the identified problem or barriers which hinders the development, faster and easier issuance of some of the products and services and the development of the sub-sectors are ethical problems, laws, managerial & legal resources and many more.

Most respondents confirmed that, the credit from the institution is very beneficiary to them and without microfinance program by their doorsteps they could not start any business on their own let alone expand the businesses nor able to pay fees of their school-going children, making deposit, improving their household consumption which all increase their standard and condition of living.

In the Furtherance of the above, it can be concluded that, through the micro-credit from the institution, many poor clients have benefited from the program especially those in the rural communities.

Finally, the women who are supposed to be targeted are rather few in most cases in the microfinance program. Targeting the majority of women is a key concern in designing any microfinance program since women and children are the most vulnerable and constitute the poor class and also have less access to credits.

8. Recommendations

Firstly, the Government should encourage technical education where students can learn different practical knowledge to help them be on their own after school and not rely on the government for a job. Again, the government should reduce the minimum capital requirement by microfinance so that more institutions will be established and also the existing ones sustained since the institutions help create jobs for the masses and give credits to most of their customers. Also, the Government should give support to collapsing microfinance to sustain them and the high-interest rates should be made moderate to encourage more investors and depositors into the institution.

Secondly, Proper credit risk management tools should be available in all microfinance institutions to help in assessing the value and worthiness of the customers/borrowers and the loan providers. Credit rating agencies should do their work properly to know which of the clients qualifies to be given credit and who to deny. Complying with regulatory rules and regulations. The microfinance sub-sector should follow the rules and regulations from the regulators. Complying with the guidelines of the regulatory framework will help the institutions to be in operations for a longer period. Training loan officers, the customers and loan beneficiaries on the use of capital can help reduce the default rate by customers and best monitoring by the officers. There should be intensive training of the management and other employees of microfinance institutions.

Finally, the researchers recommends that the beneficiaries of the loans should go strictly by the advises that the management of the microfinance institutions gives to them to promote the growth of their businesses, make a profit and be able to settle their credits within the required time. Also, customers should attend all training organized to them by the microfinance institutions management. This will help them with the use of the loans and the kind of businesses to be engaged in. The credit given to the customers by the microfinance sub-sector should not be used to settle other banks' debt and cause default problems with the institutions. Loans given should be used for the right purposes.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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